

The Nature of the Metallic Orbital and the Structure of Metals*

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Twenty three years ago it was suggested¹ that for the iron-group transition metals about 8.22 orbitals formed by hybridization of the five 3*d*, one 4*s*, and three 4*p* orbitals are used in the formation of resonating covalent bonds or for occupancy by unshared electron pairs or unpaired atomic electrons. The nature of the remaining 0.78 orbital per atom, called the metallic orbital, was discussed ten years later: it was pointed out² that the metallic orbital permits the unsynchronized resonance of covalent bonds from one interatomic position to another by the jump of one electron from an atom to an adjacent atom without the necessity for simultaneous compensatory resonance of other bonds to retain constancy of the electron numbers of the atoms. For example, in lithium metal each atom has one valence electron, permitting the formation of one covalent bond for each pair of atoms. These bonds resonate among alternative positions, mainly those between each atom and its eight nearest neighbors. If each atom were required to remain neutral, by retaining its valence electron, the stabilization in energy through the permitted synchronous bond resonance, corresponding for a square of four atoms to the two structures

would be small. Greater resonance stabilization results from unsynchronized resonance, which permits inclusion of

in the set of resonance structures. The electronic conductance and other characteristic properties of metals may be described in terms of the transfer of positive and negative charges from atom to atom accompanying the resonance of the covalent bonds.

For unsynchronized metallic resonance it is required that each neutral atom and each atom with a positive formal charge have available an unoccupied bond orbital, in order to permit acceptance of another bond. We may confidently assume that significant contributions are made only by structures in which the formal charges of the atoms are -1 , 0 , or $+1$ only (the principle of electroneutrality^{3,4}).

It was pointed out some time ago⁵ that a simple statistical calculation leads to the conclusion that for lithium metal resonance of bonds unsynchronized except for the foregoing restriction leads to 43% neutral atoms and 28.5% each Li^+ and Li^- . The experimentally based value 0.72 for the number of metallic orbitals per atom is derived from the properties of the metals chromium to copper, which have metallic valence approxi-

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mately 6 and ligancy 12 in the cubic or hexagonal closest-packed structures. The numbers of ways of distributing 5, 6, and 7 bonds among 12 positions about an atom are $12!/5!7!$, $12!/(6!)^2$, and $12!/5!7!$, respectively, which are in the ratios 6:7:6. Hence the corresponding probabilities of occurrence of M^+ , M , and M^- in the metal are 6/19, 7/19, and 6/19, which are 31.6, 36.8, and 31.6%, respectively.

For unsynchronized resonance of this sort the atoms M^+ and M , but not M^- , must have a metallic orbital. Hence we conclude that the number of metallic orbitals per atom should be about $0.316 + 0.368 = 0.684$. This value closely approximates the value 0.72 found by analysis of the magnetic properties of the metals chromium to copper and their binary alloys.

The difference between the value given by the statistical calculation and that found by experiment is in the direction of a larger fraction of uncharged atoms in the metal than that corresponding to completely unsynchronized resonance of the bonds. This result suggests that the energy required to separate the charges interferes with the motion of the electrons to some extent, so as to increase by a few percent the probability of zero charge.

The above argument permits the discussion of the metallic valence of hyperelectronic atoms to be carried out in a straightforward way. The observed bond lengths in white tin (each tin atom has four ligands at 3.016 Å, bond number 0.52, and two at 3.175 Å, bond number 0.28) correspond^{6,7} to the valence 2.64. The expected value is about 2.60, as given by the following calculation. The probabilities 0.30, 0.40, and 0.30 are found for Sn^+ , Sn , and Sn^- by the statistical treatment (assuming as a simple approximation 2, 3, or 4 bonds in 6 positions). The atoms have four outer orbitals (hybrids of the 5s orbital and the three 5p orbitals) and 3, 4, and 5 outer electrons, respectively. Hence Sn^+ can be trivalent (spp) and have its metallic orbital, Sn must be bivalent (s^2pp) to retain its metallic orbital, and Sn^- is trivalent (s^2ppp), with no metallic orbital. The weighted average of the valences is thus 2.60.

The single-bond metallic radius of tin has the value 1.399 Å for a tetrahedral orbital (Sn^+) and 1.434 Å for a p orbital (Sn and Sn^-). The appropriate value for white tin is hence 1.424 Å, which leads, with the equation:

$$D(n) = D(1) - 0.60 \text{ \AA} \log n,$$

to the values of bond numbers n quoted in the preceding paragraph.

A similar discussion can be given to other hyperelectronic metals and also buffer metals⁸. For nickel, for example, Ni^+ , Ni , and Ni^- are expected to occur in the ratio 0.28:0.44:0.28. A metallic orbital is required for Ni^+ and Ni , which have, respectively, nine and ten outer electrons to be placed in the eight stable orbitals other than the metallic orbital. This requires that Ni^+ have one unshared pair of electrons; of the other seven electrons, six are involved in bonding and the seventh has an unpaired spin that can contribute to the ferromagnetism of the metal. For Ni , with ten electrons, there are two unshared pairs and six bonding electrons; accordingly Ni contributes nothing to the ferromagnetism of the metal. For Ni^- , with all nine orbitals available for occupancy by electrons, the eleven electrons may be introduced as two electron pairs, six bonding electrons, and one unpaired atomic electron. Accordingly Ni^+ and Ni^- contribute one electron spin to the magnetic moment of the ferromagnetic metal, and, with probability 0.28 for each, the predicted saturation magnetic moment is 0.56 Bohr magnetons, plus the contribution (0.06) of the uncoupled electrons of the conduction band⁹. It is possible that an experimental check on this theory, which assigns the magnetic moment almost entirely to Ni^+ and Ni^- , could be made by a magnetic resonance experiment.

SUMMARY

The properties of the transition metals and alloys indicate that 0.72 orbital per atom is required for metallic character, in addition to the stable orbitals that are occupied by bonding electrons or atomic electrons. Consideration of the electronic structure of metal indicates that an extra orbital of this sort would be needed by the atoms M^+ and M in order to permit unsynchronized resonance of valence bonds, to the extent permitted by the restriction of the electroneutrality principle, but that M^- would not require a metallic orbital. Statistical calculations support the probabilities 0.28, 0.44, and 0.28 for M^+ , M , and M^- , respectively. The number of metallic orbitals, the sum of M^+ and M , is thus found to be about 0.72 per atom, in agreement with the value indicated by the magnetic properties of the metals and alloys.

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